

ISic1036

I.Sicily inscription 1036

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

on the wall of the 'grotta dei cavalli', Acrae

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140514

1. Ἰέρ[ω]νος.
2. βασιλέως
3. Ἰέρωνος
4. Ἀκραιῶν.
5. ΠΙΛΛΥΘΑΝ
- 6.

Edition: PHI175587

1. ΒΑΣΙΛΕΟΣ
2. ΙΕΡΟΝΟΣ
3. ΑΚΡΑΙΩΝ
4. ΕΠΙΛΛΥΘΑΝ
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492663

EDCS 39102189

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Bibliography

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